

Policy Innovation Context In The Organization And Empowerment Of Street Vendors In Baubau City, Sulawesi Tenggara Province

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 11, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 20, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Policy Implementation, Structuring, Empowerment, Street Vendors</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5228709</p>	<p><i>This research is motivated by the existence of policy innovations carried out by the local government of Baubau City in managing and empowering street vendors in Baubau City. The problem in this study is how is the context for the emergence of policy innovations for structuring and empowering street vendors (PKL) in Baubau City. The purpose of this research is to identify the context of the local government policy innovation in Baubau city in managing and empowering street vendors in Baubau City. The approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. This research is focused on the policy context in managing and empowering street vendors in Baubau City. This research is a library research with the subject of Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and Empowerment of street vendors. This research uses content analysis method. The results show that there are two contexts that encourage the innovation of Baubau municipal government policies in organizing the and empower street vendors in Baubau City, first, democracy and decentralization policies. Second, social and economic factors and demographics.</i></p>

Introduction

The ideal city development and arrangement must pay attention to various aspects such as social, economic, cultural and environmental aspects. In fact, the development and arrangement of cities often cannot keep up with the rapid development of the times so that the concepts that have been made seem to be obsolete and unable to cope with such rapid developments.

Urban development needs to prioritize aspects of the use of science, technology and innovation as a forming factor for competitiveness or what is called innovation-driven development. Development growth needs to be driven by a strategy that is not only more efficient, but promotes innovation by leveraging science, technology and innovation (innovation driven).

The development of urban development cannot be separated from the existence of economic actors. One of them is a street vendor whose existence is very dilemma. The emergence of street vendors in almost every corner of the city has created new problems and made it difficult for the city government to make arrangements. One of the cities in Indonesia that is facing a flood of street vendors is the City of Baubau.

Baubau City is one of the cities in Indonesia which has a fairly high economic growth. A strategic location that is on the golden route for Indonesian shipping that connects the Western and Eastern Regions of Indonesia, making Baubau City a city that will continue to develop rapidly. This development will cover all aspects, both physical, economic, and social aspects, which will gradually increase the status of Baubau City from a small town to a medium city and even a large city. The implication of all this will increase the complexity of the problems that occur in the city of Baubau.

From an economic perspective, the development of the city of Baubau will be followed by the economic dynamics that occur. The growth of economic activity, both in the formal and informal sectors, will be higher in proportion to the increasing needs of the community, which will gradually continue to adapt to the physical development of the city.

Economic activities that continue to develop, both in the formal and informal sectors, will have impacts which, if not anticipated and planned early on, will have negative impacts that outweigh the positive impacts. Innovative policies are needed so that negative impacts can be minimized while positive impacts can be maximized, especially in terms of orderly space utilization.

The informal sector in Kota Baubau is currently growing very rapidly. One of the informal sectors that is growing very rapidly is the street vendors (PKL). The development of street vendors can be seen to dominate the activities of other sectors in areas that are centers of community activity. It is not uncommon for the existence of street vendors on the one hand to complement public spaces. On the other hand, the existence of street vendors can bring problems to urban areas. Problems occur because of the absence of a good arrangement,

which creates an impression of slums. The problem becomes more diverse when occupying illegal lands that are not designated for trading activities, for example roads and pedestrians.

Public policy innovation as a necessity in principle and substantively can provide reinforcement in responding to and resolving problems caused by street vendors (PKL). For many, policy innovation is seen as a straightforward answer to the problem itself. Policy innovation is an alternative in the dimension of public policy in solving problems caused by street vendors (PKL).

This research is intended to examine the context of innovative policies of the local government of Baubau city in managing and empowering street vendors in Baubau City, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

Literature review

Public Sector Innovations

Innovation in the public sector context has been defined as the creation and implementation of new processes, products, services and delivery methods that result in significant improvements in the efficiency, effectiveness or quality of results (Moor & Hartley, 2008). Public administration innovations include decentralizing public administration, simplifying procedures, informatizing service delivery and improving human resource development. Therefore, the innovation process includes mechanisms that will ensure transparency and accountability of the public sector (Batalli, 2011).

Types of Innovations in the public sector include: New or development service innovations; Process innovation (changes in the manufacture of a product or service); administrative innovation (use of new policy instruments, which may be the result of changing policies); system innovation (new systems or fundamental changes from existing systems, the formation of new organizations or new patterns of cooperation and interaction); conceptual innovation (changes in the views of actors, these changes are accompanied by the use of new concepts; radical changes in rationality (Thenint, 2010).

Public sector innovation can also focus on several different aspects of the public sector value chain, although most public administrators today strongly equate innovation with technology. However, an innovation need not result in a change in technology.

Among the difficulties in introducing new practices in the public sector is the gap between political authority and administration (Adams & Hess, 2010). This not only has a negative effect on innovation but also on the effectiveness of the public sector in general. For public sector innovation to be effective it requires a strong authorization environment as well as a framework for operationalization and often requires new institutional arrangements and instruments to enable them to function effectively (Adams & Hess, 2010).

Five groups of characteristics in public sector innovation: systems approach, use of new technologies, process improvement, empowerment of staff, citizens or communities, private or voluntary sector use (Borins & Fung, 2008). Three different strategies or methods European public institutions use to innovating, namely, policy-driven methods, bottom up methods and external knowledge methods (Arundel & Hollanders, 2011).

Policy-based methods are characterized by policies that encourage innovation mandated in institutional budgets, new laws or regulations, new policy priorities. This method is used by 30.4% of institutions in Europe. This method, can be considered as a classic approach to public sector innovation (Arundel & Hollanders, 2011).

There are two general approaches to innovation. First, it focuses on the organizational and social processes that produce innovation, such as organizational structure or social and economic factors. The second treats innovation as a new product or new feature or method of production. Process innovation involves exploring and exploiting service process improvement opportunities that come from new practices both technically and changing community demands, or a combination of the two (Tarnawska&Ćwiklicki, 2012).

A number of variables have been identified as driving variables for innovation. The research results of Vigoda-Gadot et al., (2008) found that: responsiveness, leadership and vision are important antecedents of innovation in the public sector. Public sector innovation affects the trust and satisfaction levels of users of public administration, and the influence of public sector innovation on trust and satisfaction can be directly or mediated by the image of public organizations (Vigoda-Gadot et al., 2008).

With regard to the drivers of innovation in the public sector, Murray, et al (2010) have described some of the triggers and inspirations for innovation in the public sector (Murray, et al., 2010): Crisis; efficiency savings; poor performance highlights the need for changes in services; new technology; new technologies can be adapted to better meet social needs or provide more effective services. Examples include the use of computers in classrooms; new evidence; some small-scale symbolic projects can create energy points that leave cities more open to innovation.

Furthermore, there are three sets of variables to stimulate innovation, namely structural variables, culture, and human resources (Robbins, 1994). Peter Drucker (2002) tends to look at seven sources of innovative opportunity. The first four sources lie within an organization, whether a business organization or a public service agency, or within an industrial or service sector. Therefore these four sources are visible primarily to people within the industrial organization or the service sector. These four sources are basically symptoms. But they are very reliable indicators of changes that have occurred or can be made to occur with only minimal effort.

The four sources referred to are (Drucker, 2002): 1) The unexpected — unexpected successes, unexpected failures, unexpected external events; 2) Mismatch between reality as it is and reality that is assumed or "should be"; 3) Innovation based on demand processes; 4) Changes in the industrial structure or market structure that attracts everyone without realizing it. The second type of source of innovative opportunity, is a three series that involves change outside of the organization or company or industry: 1) Demographics (population change); 2) Changes in perception, mood, and meaning; 3) New knowledge, both scientific and non-scientific. The lines between the seven sources of innovative opportunity are inherently fuzzy and often blurred, and there is some overlap between them.

There are seven factors that influence innovation in Indonesia (Sumarto, 2009). First, crisis, democracy and political opportunity. Second, innovation architects and visionary leaders. Third, the existence of a support group. Fourth, the role of the central government. Fifth, citizen participation. Sixth, support and exchange between peers. Seventh, management structure and intensive structure (Sumarto, 2009). Large innovations develop are often driven by the emergence of new technologies, new types of organizations, new relationships between organizations, fundamental changes in organizations, social and cultural arrangements (Mulgan & Albury, 2003).

The innovation pattern is a function of the interaction of three complex factors: motivation; organizational culture, and the challenges of implementing innovation (Glor, 2001). In addition, there are internal and external drivers that influence public sector innovation. Internal drive is strategy, organizational climate, strategic leadership, entrepreneurship and organizational resources. External forces include political, economic, social, technological, ecological and legal factors (Agolla & Lill, 2013).

Innovation in the context of the public sector has been defined as the creation of new things (Moor & Hartley, 2008), use of new policy instruments (Thenint, 2010), and empowerment of citizens or communities, use of the private sector or voluntary (Borins & Fung, 2008). Innovation greatly contributes to the democratization process of an institution. So, although an innovation per se is a small process, it can trigger a large process, namely a state transformation (Alberti & Bertucci, 2006).

Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 18 of 2002 concerning the National System for Research, Development and Application of Science and Technology, defines innovation as a research, development, and / or engineering activity aimed at developing practical applications of new scientific values and contexts, or methods, to apply existing science and technology to a product or production process.

In the context of this research, innovation is defined as a way to solve a problem in a way that has not or has not been done before.

Public policy

Basically there are many limitations or definitions regarding what is meant by public policy. In addition to the definition of public policy which is generally known as a legal or regulatory system made by the government on certain issues, public policy has been conceptualized in various ways according to the objectives and characteristics of the situation faced by the speaker or writer. More formally, Anderson, JE (2003) defines policy as a relatively stable and purposeful action followed by an actor or group of actors in dealing with a problem or problem of concern. This definition helps explain what constitutes public policy and what is not. The important attributes of public policy are, first, public policy contains government actions, second, public policy has a specific goal, and third, public policy is aimed at dealing with certain problems faced by the public.

Thomas R Dye (1995) defines public policy as "whatever the government chooses to do or not to do." This definition emphasizes that public policy is about the embodiment of "action" and is not a mere statement of the will of the government or public officials. the government not to do something is also a public policy because it has the same influence (impact) as the government's choice to do something.

Specifically, public policy has a number of main characteristics: Policy is what the government chooses to do or not do about a particular problem or problem; policies can be in the form of legal systems, laws, or regulations, or government regulations, regional regulations that regulate a particular problem or problem; policies are made in response to several types of problems or problems that require government involvement to reach a solution; policy oriented to a goal or desired state, such as solving a problem. In the end, policies are made by government entities.

Creating a definition of public policy that is inclusive is not an easy task. However, based on the opinion of experts, it can be concluded that public policy is a series of actions taken or not carried out by the government which is oriented towards certain goals in order to solve public problems or in the public interest. Policies to do something are usually contained in statutory provisions or regulations, government regulations, regional regulations made by the government so that they have a binding and coercive nature. Public policies in this context are regional regulations made by local governments for the benefit of local communities. so that they can live, and participate in broad regional development.

Policy innovation as an approach that can help increase the capacity of the public sector to deal productively and sustainably with public problems. In this context, public policy innovation can be interpreted as government

action that aims to solve problems in ways that have not or have not previously been applied to citizens or society. Referring to some of these opinions, Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and empowering street vendors can be categorized as an innovative policy because in principle it contains something new, namely bringing new values that regulate the behavior and economic activities of the community, and the business world Bauba City especially in solving the problem of street vendors.

Method

This research was conducted in Baubau City, Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia in 2015. The approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. This research is focused on the policy context in managing and empowering street vendors in Baubau City, Southeast Sulawesi Province. This research is a library research with the main subject of Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and Empowerment of street vendors. Libraries can be broadly defined as books, articles, documents, regulations. This research uses content analysis method. The data under study requires a descriptive explanation. The data studied are in the form of content contained in the Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and empowering street vendors. Inference is an activity to interpret data according to the context, this is because the meaning of a content or text is related to the context. Inference is carried out first by understanding the meaning of the context in Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and empowering street vendors. Then proceed with understanding the meaning outside the text which is supported by the results of observations.

Result and Discussion

The policy of structuring and empowering street vendors in Baubau City which is contained in the Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and empowering street vendors is a policy that aims to create a conducive regional climate, especially for community economic activities and the business world.

The making of Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and empowering street vendors cannot be separated from several contexts, namely:

1. Context of democracy and decentralization policy

Democracy and political opportunity are among the factors that influence innovation (Sumarto, 2009). The process of democratization in Indonesia that has lasted more than two decades, since the reform era in 1998, has fundamentally changed the political system and the role of the state and society. This phenomenon is a consequence of a policy change from a centralized model to a decentralized one (regional autonomy). This political change was marked by the replacement of Law Number 5 of 1974 concerning the principles of governance in the regions which was replaced by Law Number 22 of 1999 concerning regional governance. Because after being implemented for decades, Law Number 5 of 1974 is deemed no longer in accordance with the principles of implementing regional autonomy and the development of conditions so it needs to be replaced.

The decentralization policy was triggered by political pressures during the reform era in 1999. The essence of the decentralization policy is aimed at improving the welfare of the community through a strategy of providing services to the public that is more effective and efficient and the acceleration of growth and the development of an increasingly fast regional potential. Each autonomous region is encouraged and spurred to grow and develop independently according to the authority given to manage the potential of their respective regions.

One of the aspects in regional planning is the formation of new regions. The formation of regions is basically intended to improve public services in order to accelerate the realization of the welfare of the people of the Administrative City of Baubau to obtain the status as a city area - as an autonomous region, precisely on June 21, 2001 based on Law Number 13 of 2001. Number 40 of 1981 concerning the Establishment of the Administrative City of Baubau, previously the Administrative City of Baubau was part of the autonomous region of Buton Regency.

The consideration of the expansion of the Baubau City area as stated in Law Number 13 of 2001 is the result of the development and progress of Southeast Sulawesi Province in general and Buton Regency in particular as well as the aspirations that develop in society to improve welfare by regulating and managing their own households, organizing governance, implementation of development, community services, as well as economic progress, regional potential, socio-culture, socio-politics, population, area size, and other considerations.

Simplistically it can be said that the most significant policy to encourage innovation in the area of Baubau City is the decentralization policy, namely Law Number 22 Year 1999. This policy changes the administration of government from previously centralized to decentralized. The real effect of the decentralization policy is the administration of government from previously centralized to decentralized.

Normatively, referring to Law Number 22 Year 1999, decentralization is defined as the handover of governmental authority by the government to autonomous regions to regulate and manage governmental affairs in the system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

In 2004, Law No. 22/1999 was amended by Law No. 32/2004. The decentralization policy as stated in Law No. 32/2004 is directed at accelerating the realization of community welfare through improvement, service, empowerment, and community participation, as well as increasing regional competitiveness by taking into account the principles of democracy, equity, justice, privileges and specialties of a region in the system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

Based on the normative definition above, in principle, Law Number 32 Year 2004 regulates the implementation of regional government which prioritizes the implementation of the decentralization principle by providing opportunities and flexibility for regions to carry out regional autonomy. Through regional autonomy, the community not only has a greater opportunity to participate in government affairs, but also has wider access to participate in overseeing the running of government and development.

In principle, Law Number 32 Year 2004 regulates the implementation of regional government that prioritizes the implementation of the decentralization principle by providing opportunities and flexibility for regions to carry out regional autonomy. Through regional autonomy, the community not only has a greater opportunity to participate in government affairs, but also has wider access to participate in overseeing the running of government and development.

In 2014 Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government was issued to replace Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government. Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government provides opportunities for local governments to innovate. Precisely in article 386 which states that "in the context of improving the performance of the regional administration, regional governments can make innovations". The innovation referred to is all forms of reform in the implementation of Regional Government. As mandated by Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, innovation is an important element in the implementation of Regional Government. Innovation determines the high competitiveness of a region / country.

In line with the implementation of regional autonomy which gives regional governments the authority to formulate policies, the role of public officials in the regions in carrying out public policy innovations will increase.

Contextually, it can be seen that the decentralization policy is a structural factor that influences the policy of structuring and empowering street vendors in Baubau City which is stated in the Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Arrangement and empowerment of street vendors. This is in line with the view of Robbins (1994) that structural factors and encourages innovation. This method according to Arundel & Hollanders (2011) is called a policy-driven method.

2. Socio-economic and demographic context

Social and economic context (Tarnawska&Ćwiklicki, 2012), and demographics (Drucker, 2002) are factors that can produce innovation. In general, urban areas are a concentration of residential areas from various economic and social activities and have a very important role in social life. On the one hand, the economic and social activities of the population, which are accompanied by high needs, increasingly require space to increase population activities, thus causing increased space to support informal sector activities. One of the informal sector is street vendors (PKL).

According to the Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and empowering street vendors. Street vendors (PKL) are business actors who carry out trading businesses using movable or immovable business facilities, using city infrastructure, social facilities, public facilities, land and buildings owned by the Government and / or the private sector which are temporary or not permanent.

In general, street vendors are located in the center of Baubau City, namely in Wolio, Murhum, Batupoaro, Betoambari and Kokalukuna Districts. This is due to the concentration of housing and settlements in these 4 sub-districts. The implication is the high population circulation around the area which is the main attraction for street vendors (PKL).

An important issue of development in the City of Baubau is the proliferation of street vendors in various corners of the city of Baubau which is inseparable from the rapid development of the population of the city of Baubau that has become a magnet that attracts economic actors to carry out business activities in Baubau City.

On the one hand, the existence of street vendors is recognized as an economic potential that cannot be ignored. Street vendors who are able to absorb a large number of workers and provide the necessities of life for the community. But on the other hand, the existence of street vendors is considered to disturb the beauty and order of the City environment. One of the efforts of the Baubau City local government in addressing this matter is the issuance of the Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and empowering street vendors. The policy of structuring and empowering street vendors in Baubau City is related to the goal of creating a conducive regional climate, particularly for the economic activities of the community and the business world.

According to the Baubau City regional regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning the arrangement and empowerment of street vendors, the arrangement of street vendors is an effort made by the local government through the determination of the target location to determine, transfer, control and eliminate street vendors' locations by taking into account the public, social, aesthetic, and health interests, economy, security, order, environmental cleanliness and in accordance with statutory regulations. PKL empowerment is an effort made by the Regional Government, the business world, and the community in synergy in the form of fostering a business climate and developing business for street vendors so that they are able to grow and develop both in quality and quantity of their business

Thus, in general, the socio-economic and demographic factors have encouraged the innovation of structuring and empowering policies for limousine traders in Baubau City which is contained in the Baubau City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2015 concerning Structuring and empowering street vendors. In this case the socioeconomic context is an important contributor to encouraging innovation (Tarnawska&Ćwiklicki, 2012). Meanwhile, Drucker (2002) also states that demographics are a source of opportunities for innovation.

Conclusion

There are two contexts of policy innovation on structuring and empowering street vendors in Baubau City. First, the decentralization policy as a structural factor that encourages policy innovation. Second, social and economic factors as well as demographics are also factors that encourage the policy of structuring and empowering limousine traders in Baubau City.

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